

Poly Power Wave Energy Converter

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INTRODUCTION

Converting the energy of the ocean has been a challenge for decades. In this project we have been working with this problem in a whole new way. The goal of the project has been to implement the Danfoss Poly Power elastomer in one of the existing wave energy converting systems.

During the project several setups have been tested in the wave tank on our 1:60 model. We have optimized the utilization of the waves and tried to give a rough estimate on the energy output of a real-size Wave Energy Converter.

Wave testing 1:60 model of the Wave Energy Converter